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Peer review by Swabian Research completed on June 12th, 2023.

SHORT REPORT

Hyperlactatemia in mitochondrial disease manifesting as postprandial narcolepsy: the biological background, the risk of misdiagnosis, and implications in dual-diagnosis patients

Abstract

With this short report we explore the intriguing association between hyperlactatemia, a common metabolic disturbance found in patients with mitochondrial disease, and narcolepsy-like symptoms. We delve into the biological mechanisms involved, the risk of misdiagnosing this as primary narcolepsy, and the unique challenges faced by patients suffering from both conditions.

Lactate induced sleep attacks

Mitochondrial diseases, disorders linked to defects in the mitochondrial respiratory chain, often lead to a wide array of clinical manifestations due to the critical role of mitochondria in cellular energy production.

One common metabolic aberration in these diseases is hyperlactatemia, characterized by an excessive level of lactate in the blood. (>2,2 mmol/l in whole blood). The latter results from compromised oxidative phosphorylation, forcing cells to rely on less efficient anaerobic glycolysis, producing lactate as a byproduct. In recent years, an

intriguing clinical manifestation of hyperlactatemia in mitochondrial disease has been observed, which presents with narcolepsy-like symptoms. Narcolepsy is a chronic neurological disorder characterized by excessive daytime sleepiness, sudden loss of muscle tone (cataplexy), sleep paralysis, and hallucinations. The classical form of narcolepsy is caused by the loss of neurons producing hypocretin (also known as orexin), a neuropeptide that plays a pivotal role in wakefulness and the sleep-wake cycle (Urrila et al. 2004).

Due our observation in the past years it has to be postulated that hyperlactatemia-induced narcolepsy-like symptoms result from a disruption of the same hypocretin system. Mitochondria are abundant in hypocretin neurons, underscoring their very high energy demand. In the context of mitochondrial disease, compromised energy production may cause neuronal dysfunction or loss, resembling the hypocretin deficiency seen in primary narcolepsy (Diamandis, Honda, Balaskas, 2021).

This symptom overlap poses significant diagnostic challenges. Clinicians must be cautious not to hastily attribute excessive sleepiness and other narcolepsy-like symptoms in a patient with mitochondrial disease solely to primary narcolepsy. It's vital to consider hyperlactatemia-induced neuronal dysfunction as a potential differential diagnosis (Papadopoulos, Honda et al. 2021).

In patients diagnosed with both mitochondrial (cytopathy) disease-related hyperlactatemia and narcolepsy, the clinical picture can be even more complex. These patients may suffer an additive effect of primary hypocretin deficiency and additional hypocretin neuronal stress due to mitochondrial dysfunction (Sikder et al. 2007) This may exacerbate the severity of

their symptoms and complicate their treatment.

Management in these scenarios requires a holistic and integrative approach, addressing both the underlying mitochondrial disorder and narcolepsy. Therapeutic strategies may involve lifestyle modifications, symptomatic treatment for narcolepsy (stimulants or selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors), and strategies aimed at mitochondrial disease (such as coenzyme Q10, vitamin B1, and other dietary supplements). Nevertheless, comprehensive research is warranted to further understand this intricate relationship and develop tailored therapeutic approaches.

Conclusion

The overlap of hyperlactatemia-induced narcolepsy-like symptoms in mitochondrial disease presents a very fascinating yet challenging scenario. It calls for a better understanding of the biological mechanisms involved, a high index of suspicion to avoid misdiagnosis, and a careful, integrated approach to manage those who suffer from both conditions.

Conflicts of interest

None.

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